

The Multifaceted Nature of Astrocytes: From Ancillary Cells To Neural Circuitry

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Abstract- Throughout the history of the ascent of cognitive sciences, cells of the robust and rather resourceful bio-entity we call the brain have enjoyed particular attention, deliberation and scrutiny. Among these are the tiles that pile up throughout CNS by outnumbering neurons fivefold, called Astrocytes. (Michael V et al 2009) [1] Astrocytes played a passive role in the learning of neuroscience, however, recent studies have invoked compelling novelty that attends more to their contribution as astrocyte-assisted neural signalling, astrocyte-associated immunological activity (Dong et al 2001) [2] and Ca-based form of excitability (Fiacco TA et al 2008). [3]

This article will explore the contrast among the historical remodelings regarding the understanding of astrocyte molecular biology while focusing on the review of avant-garde updates central to astrocyte functioning. It is already well put by Harold K Kimelberg (2004) [4], "Astrocytes had been the initial neuroglia of Ramón y Cajal but even after 100 years there is no adequate interpretation of what should comprise these cells," Surely more systematic examination into this would extract an integrated and thorough understanding of astrocytes but this could borrow more time, perhaps years. This article puts into perspective, the manifold scope of astrocyte biology by producing organized discussions regarding several essential themes such as astrocytes as intermediaries to the regulation of neurodegenerative diseases, neural modulation and discoveries of astrocyte-associated therapeutic targets.

Keywords- Astrocyte biology, Astrocyte network, Synaptic plasticity, Astrocyte functioning, Neurological disorders.

I. INTRODUCTION

The complex cellular grid of the brain can be roughly put as two categories: the neuroglia and the neurons. When this binary allotment for all the neural cells was introduced, neuroglia was primarily interpreted as accessory support and nutrition-providing agency. Astrocytes are one type of neuroglial cell, although, both neurons and astrocytes have

rather similar arboreal structures (see Fig. 1) and dynamic network-forming potential.

In divergence to the view of the Astrocytes as ancillary cells in the brain, secondary to neurons, recent studies have brought into the limelight, the view of the inclusion of astrocytes into neural circuits. Astrocyte network is also found to be intertwined as a complex net that regulates vasoactive particles with the effect of prostaglandin, nitric oxide, adenosine, calcium signalling and reactive oxygen species. The addition of such learning has influenced our idea of brain complexity over the past two decades.

Fig. 1. A neuron and an astrocyte show a broad similarity in their arborized forms. The later segment (b) of the neuron's long axonal and (a) processes of a typical astrocyte are shown in this drawing.

Astrocytes heterogeneity theory has shown astrocytes to have diverse molecular, morphological, and functional characteristics. This means that astrocytes within various distinct brain regions, at successive developmental phases, and pathological conditions may have distinct properties and functions. The heterogeneity of astrocytes also influences various functions of astrocytes like calcium signalling, potassium buffering and synaptic pruning which will be discussed in detail in this article. Plasticity, Astrocyte functioning, Neurological disorders.

II. HISTORICAL OVERVIEW OF ASTROCYTE BIOLOGY

1. 1870s to 1890s: The development of staining techniques was critical especially for the research by R Cajal and overall advances in the understanding of astrocytes biology. Golgi stain which involved impregnating neurons with silver, which highlighted their intricate branching structures and Nissi stain which required staining the RNA-rich structures within neurons called Nissi bodies with a basic dye, showed great promise in later elevation, not just within the context of astrocyte biology but in the overall neural research. [5][6]
2. 1893: A century ago R Cajal published two studies to expound on the nature of glial cells: “Algo sobre la significación funcional de la neuroglia” (Something about the physiological significance of neuroglia) [7] in 1897 and “Contribución al conocimiento de la neuroglia del cerebro humano” (A contribution to the understanding of neuroglia of the human brain) [8] in 1913. Making a mesh of connections surrounding blood vessels and neurons, astrocytes with somal projections entangle with both of these cellular components. Cajal suggested the insulation theory that considered astrocytes as insulating agencies providing spacial separation and mechanical support. The insulation theory did not show promise at proving its prospect in further studies in astrocyte biology.
3. 1920s to 1930s: With vivid descriptions of the morphology of astrocytes, Carl Lorente de Nó proposed that Astrocytes react to the energy demands by upregulating glycolysis, and respiration. His hypothesis of the respiratory response of astrocytes to the brain’s oxygen consumption was proved exact by further studies. [9][10]
4. 1950s to 1960s: Astrocytes form specialized gap junctions by deploying the hexameric protein units forming hollow linkages with adjacent cells to facilitate direct communication. These gap junctions brought astrocytes into the limelight as neuron-aiding agencies through successive studies by electron microscopy and brain tissue culture. [11]
5. 1970s to 1980s: As histological techniques advanced, the glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP), a signature astrocyte protein for structural support, absent in other glial cells and aquaporin-4 (AQP4) required for the movement of water in the cytosol were identified. These studies kept forward still a widened view of astrocyte

biology with regard to their functions, including regulating extracellular ion concentrations, providing metabolic support to neurons, and modulating synaptic transmission.

6. 1990s to present: Further discoveries regarding astrocytes have briskly broadened our understanding of astrocytes, with new advances about their roles in synaptic pruning, potassium buffering, the pathogenesis of diseases such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's and a few more which will be discussed further in this article. Advancements in imaging techniques—two-photon microscopy functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI), and more as such have also allowed researchers to study astrocytes in living biosystems.

III. DYNAMIC NETWORKS IN ASTROCYTES

In the 1970s, the newly found appeal to the dynamic nature of astrocytes after the recognition of a large number of gap junctions can be encapsulated in a statement: “Adjacent glial cells, however, including those of mammals, are linked to each other by gap junctions. In this respect they simulate epithelial or gland cells or heart muscles fibres” (From neuron to brain by SW Kuffler et al) [12] Astrocytes make a dynamic network associated with neurons and blood vessels and preside over these through the effect of vasoactive and ionic species. They also communicate using protein tunnels known as gap junctions that are structured using a specialized class of proteins called connexion (Cx). Eleven Cxs have been identified in the brains of vertebrates, which makes up more than half of the 21 total Cxs discovered so far [13][14]. The lack of Cxs in neurons has been recently validated through in situ hybridization studies carried out on adult rats [15] which makes astrocytes primarily associated with Cxs. In addition to their role as gap junction channels, Cxs can also act as hemichannels, facilitating the exchange of heme molecules between the cytoplasmic and extracellular regions. However, these hemichannels are sometimes targeted for therapeutic inhibition [16][17]. In an adult brain, the two connexins that form a major domain of gap junctions are Cx43 (aka GJA1) and Cx30 (aka GJB6) [18]. Cxs also perform other glial functions, like adhesion as well as modulation of purinergic receptors which are a class of membrane receptors associated with neural signalling [19].

Oculodentodigital dysplasia (ODDD) is a uncommon inherited disorder that is expressed as incomplete formation of the face, eyes, limbs including dentition. ODDDD is acquired from mutations in the Cx43 gene that codes for the Cx43 protein. Mutations in astrocytic connexin expression are also studied in relation with with Alzheimer's

disease, Parkinson's disease, and multiple sclerosis. In these disorders, altered connexin expression may add to the disruption of normal astrocytic function, leading to neuroinflammation, neuronal dysfunction, and cell death. [20]

Connexin channels are used to the exchange ions like potassium and calcium, release gasotransmitters, provide neurons metabolites, and synchronization of electricity. Overall, the dynamic network of astrocytes facilitated by connexins plays a crucial role in supporting brain function and responding to changes in the brain. This network is considered of high significance for maintaining healthy neuronal connectivity and synaptic plasticity.

IV. ASTROCYTE HETEROGENEITY THEORY

Throughout history, astrocytes have been considered the homogeneous group of specialised cells that takes part in neurovascular connectivity. Although, some studies interestingly claim that astrocytes possess heterogeneity not only across the brain regions but within the brain regions as well. [21].

Reactive astrocytes are a type of astrocytes that become activated for the feedback to injury or disease in the central nervous system. Liddelow et al. (2017) [22] conducted a study using transcriptomic and morphological analyses to investigate the diversity of astrocytes in mouse and human brains. They recognized two major types of reactive astrocytes, termed A1 and A2, based on their gene expression profiles. A1 astrocytes were found to be induced by neuroinflammation and were associated with a detrimental response, while A2 astrocytes were induced by developmental and homeostatic cues and were associated with a neuroprotective response. This captures the heterogeneity of astrocytes aptly.

Roots of astrocyte heterogeneity could be traced back to the 1990s when studies began to reveal morphological dissimilarities and differences in the expression of proteins specific to astrocytes along different brain regions during development. For example, astrocytes in the cerebellum were found to have a distinct stellate morphology, while those in the hippocampus were more ramified. [23] Astrocytes in the optic nerve express some proteins that are unique only to these astrocytes, like—optic nerve head astrocyte-specific protein (ONHASP) involved in optic nerve head remodelling [24], optic nerve astrocyte marker (OAM) that helps to maintain optic nerve structure, optic nerve astrocyte elevated gene-1 (OEG-1) that may play role in optic nerve repair and regeneration etc. [25]

Table 1: Investigating research in astrocyte heterogeneity:

Research	Outcomes
Oberheim et al. (2009) [26] conducted a study using immunohistochemistry and electron microscopy to investigate the diversity of astrocytes in the rat brain. It's important to note that Oberheim et al, because they used different methods than the more recent studies that utilized single-cell RNA sequencing, their findings are not directly comparable to those of Zeisel et al., Morel et al., or Liddelow et al.	Two types of astrocytes were identified: protoplasmic astrocytes and fibrous astrocytes. Protoplasmic astrocytes were found in the grey matter and had short, broader processes that formed a dense network by ensheathing the synapses. Fibrous astrocytes, were found in white matter and had long, thin processes that ran parallel to axons.
Anderson et al. in 2014 [27] identified two subpopulations of astrocytes in the mouse cortex using single-cell RNA sequencing.	The two subpopulations were called type 1 and type 2 astrocytes. Type 1 astrocytes were found to express high levels of genes related to ion channels, while type 2 astrocytes expressed higher levels of genes related to protein synthesis and vesicular transport. Additionally, the researchers found that type 1 astrocytes were localized predominantly in the grey matter, while type 2 astrocytes were localized more in and the proximity of the white matter.
Zeisel et al. (2018) [28] used single-cell RNA sequencing to analyze astrocytes in the mouse brain based on gene expression profiles.	They identified five major types of astrocytes namely fibrous astrocytes, protoplasmic astrocytes, velate astrocytes, marginal astrocytes, and interlaminar astrocytes. Additionally, they found that astrocytes in distant

	brain regions exhibited unique gene expression profiles, suggesting functional specialization.
Morel et al. (2019) [29] conducted a study using single-cell RNA sequencing to explore the diversity of astrocytes in the mouse cortex.	They identified seven major types of astrocytes which were fibrous astrocytes, protoplasmic astrocytes, velate astrocytes, marginal astrocytes, interlaminar astrocytes, and a newly identified intermediate astrocyte. This type was characterized by the expression of a unique set of genes that distinguished it from the other types. It's significant to note that since the publication of this research, further studies have expanded upon these findings.
Chung et al. (2020) [30] conducted a study using single-cell RNA sequencing used for investigating the diversity of astrocytes in the mouse and human brains.	They identified they identified seven subtypes of astrocytes of the mouse brain: fibrous astrocytes, protoplasmic astrocytes, interlaminar astrocytes, velate astrocytes, marginal astrocytes, hippocampal radial glia-like astrocytes, and cerebellar Bergmann glia-like astrocytes.
Cao, Junyue, et al (2017) [31] used single-cell RNA sequencing to investigate the diversity of astrocytes in the human brain.	They identified four main types of astrocytes: fibrous astrocytes, protoplasmic astrocytes, velate astrocytes and intermediate astrocytes that were characterized by intermediate features between fibrous and protoplasmic astrocytes. This subtype was found to be enriched in the human cerebral cortex and expressed genes associated with synaptic function and plasticity.

The discovery of astrocyte heterogeneity has important implications for our learning of CNS functionality and pathogenesis. It suggests that different subtypes of astrocytes may play specialized roles in administering synaptic transmission, neurovascular coupling, and other operations critical for normal brain function. Additionally, dysregulation

of specific subtypes of astrocytes are explored in several neurological disorders, including Alzheimer's disease and multiple sclerosis. Therefore, further research into astrocyte heterogeneity may cater to new insights into the underlying mechanisms of these diseases and potential targets for therapeutic intervention.

V.ASTROCYTE CALCIUMIN NEUROTRANSMISSION

Calcium signalling is a key operation in astrocyte function and is involved in a wide range of astrocyte-mediated processes, including synaptic transmission, gliotransmitter release, and regulation of cerebral blood flow. Astrocytes are equipped with the ability to respond to synaptic activity through calcium signaling, a phenomenon known as calcium excitability. [32-35]

Calcium signalling in astrocytes can be triggered by many extracellular stimuli. One such example is neurotransmitter-initiated calcium signalling. When axon hillock fires an action potential, axon terminals release neurotransmitters such as glutamate or GABA into the synaptic cleft. These neurotransmitters from the synaptic cleft bind to receptors (eg GPCRs, metabotropic glutamate receptors, NMDA, isotropic receptors) on the astrocyte membrane, triggering the release of calcium from intracellular regions like the endoplasmic reticulum into the astrocytic cytoplasm. This can also be caused by the influx of calcium ions within the Astrocyte from extracellular space via various membrane channels and transporters (eg. SOCC). [36][37] Calcium influx also occurs due to temperature, pressure change via transient receptor potential channels (TPC) [38], and pH change via two-pore calcium channels (TPC). [39] This calcium signal can then propagate to astrocytes in proximity via gap junctions, allowing intercellular communication and coordination of astrocytic activity. [40] Such signalling can spread over large distances within the astrocytic network. [41] This long-range glial signalling can have a profound effect on overall neural assembly and neurovascular connections.

The intracellular rise in calcium ions in astrocytes, apart from creating a calcium wave among other astrocytes, can also exocytose a class of neurotransmitters called gliotransmitters. [42] Some of the most well-studied gliotransmitters include glutamate, D-serine, adenosine, ATP, and GABA. These molecules can modulate neural activity by acting on various neural receptors.

There are several mechanisms suggested by various studies to illuminate the function of gliotransmitters like glutamate to bring change in synaptic plasticity.

- i. Regulating presynaptic function: Astrocytes can also modulate synaptic plasticity by regulating presynaptic function. For example, astrocytes can release glutamate, which can activate presynaptic mGluR receptors, leading to a reduction in presynaptic release probability and a decrease in synaptic strength.
- ii. Regulating synaptic strength through postsynaptic receptors: Astrocyte-derived glutamate has been shown to regulate synaptic strength by modulating glutamate receptors on postsynaptic neurons. Specifically, astrocyte-derived glutamate can activate the NMDA subtype of glutamate receptor, leading to an escalation in intracellular calcium levels and the activation of downstream signalling pathways that modulate synaptic strength and plasticity.
- iii. Regulating presynaptic and postsynaptic receptors: Astrocytes release glutamate, which can act on postsynaptic neurons and also take up glutamate from the extracellular space and convert it to glutamine, which can be released and taken up by presynaptic neurons to regulate neurotransmitter synthesis and release. [43]

All the aforementioned ways which elevate Ca^{2+} levels, consequently, can trigger astrocytes to release calcium ions via various channels like glutamate-permeable channels. Astrocytes also have sodium-calcium exchangers, which allow the trade of sodium ions for calcium ions. [44] This process can lead to calcium release from astrocytes. Astrocytes express ryanodine receptors, which can release calcium from intracellular stores. They are activated by various signaling pathways, such as inositol triphosphate (IP3) and ryanodine receptor agonists that are negatively modulated by neuron

Figure. 2. Calcium signalling in astrocytes. (a) Calcium influx into astrocyte by neuron synapse occurs when neurons release

- (b) Calcium intake into astrocytes from extracellular space occurs through various mechanisms such as store-operated calcium entry, receptor-mediated calcium entry, and non-specific calcium channels.
- (c) Astrocytes store calcium in the endoplasmic reticulum, where it can be rapidly released back into the cytosol to regulate various cellular processes.
- (d) Astrocytes can secrete calcium, which initiates a calcium wave that propagates through the astrocytic network.
- (e) Astrocytes can also secrete calcium into the extracellular membrane to modulate synaptic transmission and plasticity.
- (f) Calcium in astrocytes can activate various signaling pathways that lead to the release of gliotransmitters, such as glutamate and ATP, which can affect neuronal activity and synaptic transmission.

All in all, astrocyte calcium can be a causative agent for the following effects:

1. Release of gliotransmitters: Calcium signals in astrocytes can trigger the release of gliotransmitters that have been already discussed herein.
2. Generation of calcium waves: Calcium waves that spread to neighbouring astrocytes allows rapid communication and coordinated activity.
3. Regulation of blood flow: Calcium signals in astrocytes can regulate cerebral blood flow which will be discussed further in this article.
4. Energy feed to Neurons: Calcium signals can result in the intake of glucose and lactate from bloodstreams and use these as resources to induce energy into the neurons. [46]
5. Maintenance of extracellular ion balance: Calcium signals in astrocytes can maintain homeostasis by regulating the extracellular concentration of potassium ions.
6. Neuroprotection: Calcium signals in astrocytes can trigger the release of neuroprotective factors. Some examples of these factors are brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) and glial cell line-derived neurotrophic factor (GDNF). [47]
7. Regulation of synaptic pruning: Calcium signals in astrocytes have been implicated in the regulation of synaptic pruning.
8. Modulation of neural activity: Calcium signals in astrocytes can modulate the activity of nearby neurons, for example by regulating the release of neurotransmitters or by modifying the properties of synapses.

VII. POTASSIUM BUFFERING IN ASTROCYTES

Astrocytes maintain homeostasis of the extracellular membrane by the intake of biomolecules from the extracellular matrix that may cause disturbance in the concentration gradient.

Excitatory depolarisation in the neurons generates an action potential by changing the electrochemical gradient across the neuronal membrane. The Na⁺/K⁺ pump helps restore the resting membrane potential of the neuron after an action potential. However, this does not play a significant role in the buffering of K⁺ ions released during neuronal activity. This can lead to extracellular potassium accumulation thus causing depolarization and accidental firing of nearby neurons. [48] Leaky channels on the neurons that are always kept open and allow passive movement of K⁺ ions, also contribute to this accumulation of K⁺. Along with neurons, also other glial cells, blood vessels and other astrocytes can also release potassium. Neurons exocytose neurotransmitters, such as glutamate, that can stimulate the release of potassium ions from other glial cells. Blood vessels also release potassium due to the activity of endothelial and smooth muscle cells. [49] Additionally, astrocytes can release potassium ions themselves, which can then be taken in by neighbouring astrocytes or other glial cells for buffering purposes. This potassium buildup can cause neuronal hyperexcitability and seizures which are avoided by potassium buffering by astrocytes. [50]

Astrocytes have various ion exchange channels on their membranes, in this case, Kir4.1, sodium-potassium-chloride cotransporter channel 1 (NKCC1) and sodium-potassium ATPase pump (Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase pump). These are responsible for the influx of potassium ions from the extracellular space into astrocyte cytosol. Kir4.1 is an inwardly rectifying potassium channel that is highly expressed in astrocytes. [51] NKCC1 can transport potassium ions into astrocytes in exchange for sodium and chloride ions. [52] Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase is also responsible for pumping potassium ions into the cell. K⁺ ions are isolated and stored in the endoplasmic reticulum, mitochondria and cytosol.

Channels like volume-regulated anion channels (VRAC) and K₂P channels which are pore domain potassium channels participate in the efflux of potassium out of the Astrocyte cell. VRAC is activated in response to cell swelling when astrocytes take up excess potassium ions. The activation of VRAC allows for the efflux of potassium ions and other solutes, helping to restore homeostasis with regard to cell volume and maintain proper ion balance. [53]

The study Machado et al. (2019) [54] researched the primary stages of Alzheimer's disease and the contribution of

astrocyte-neuron interactions. The researchers found that aged astrocytes underwent altered morphology and reduced expression of key astrocytic markers, which may contribute to their reduced ability to buffer potassium ions. In addition, the study found that astrocytes in regions with more chronic Alzheimer's disease had more impairment in their potassium buffering capacity compared to regions with less severe Alzheimer's disease. A study published in the Journal of Alzheimer's Disease in 2018 (Simpson et al., 2018) [55] explored a similar context. The researchers found that aged mice had a reduced ability to buffer potassium in the hippocampus compared to young mice, and this was associated with increased amyloid beta accumulation, which is a hallmark of Alzheimer's disease pathology. Therefore, potassium buffering is found to be closely associated with Alzheimer's disease.

The process from the intake of potassium to its release is regulated by various signaling pathways. Some of them are as follows—

1. Glutamatergic signalling: Glutamate release from neurons can activate the signature receptors of glutamate—NMDA on astrocytes, leading to calcium signalling and subsequent release of potassium channels and transporters. [56]
2. Adenosine signalling: Adenosine produced from ATP activates A₁ receptors on astrocytes, triggering potassium uptake via Kir4.1 channels. [57]
3. GABAergic signalling: GABA released from neurons can activate GABAB receptors on astrocytes that lead to potassium uptake via Kir4.1 channels. [58]
4. Cytokine signalling: Cytokines produced during inflammation, can affect the function of potassium channels and transporters in astrocytes, leading to changes in potassium buffering capacity. [59]
5. Calcium signalling triggers potassium buffering: Increases in intracellular calcium levels in astrocytes activate various potassium channels, which leads to the release of potassium ions from the astrocytes to the extracellular space. [60]
6. Purinergic signalling: The P₂ receptors are activated by extracellular ATP levels which influence K⁺ channels and transporters on Astrocyte. [61]

Fig. 3. Potassium buffering in astrocytes. (a) Astrocytes can uptake potassium ions from the neural endings close to the synapse (b) They are stored in mitochondria and the endoplasmic reticulum, allowing for dynamic regulation of potassium homeostasis in the brain. (c) Astrocytes can release potassium ions, which can act on neurons and other glial cells, contributing to synaptic plasticity and network excitability. (d) The potassium released by astrocytes can be redistributed to various regions, such as blood capillaries, cerebrospinal fluid, and neurons, helping to maintain potassium balance in the brain.

The heterogeneity and calcium excitability that have been already studied herein majorly influence potassium buffering.

- i. Potassium buffering stimulated by calcium signalling in astrocytes: The uptake of calcium in astrocytes resultantly causes various potassium-expelling channels to open, which leads to the release of potassium ions from the astrocytes to the extracellular space. [62]
- ii. Potassium buffering affects calcium signalling in neurons: The extracellular buildup of potassium ions due to buffering can influence the excitability of nearby neurons, which may impact calcium signalling in those neurons. [63]
- iii. Astrocyte heterogeneity may impact potassium buffering: Recent studies have identified subpopulations of astrocytes with different potassium buffering capacities, indicating that the ability to buffer potassium may vary between astrocyte subtypes. A study in *The Journal of neuroscience* explores this through its findings—potassium buffering protein, Kir4.1, in different subpopulations of astrocytes in the rat brain. [64]

The balance between potassium uptake and intake is critical for maintaining the homeostasis of extracellular potassium levels, which is essential for neuronal function. Dysregulation of potassium buffering can lead to various neurological disorders, including epilepsy and stroke.

VII. SYNAPTIC PRUNING BY ASTROCYTES

Synaptic pruning is the process by which unnecessary or unwanted synapses are eliminated. During early development, the brain produces an abundance of synapses to ensure that all possible connections are made. However, not all of these connections are necessary for proper brain function. Having too many synapses can actually interfere with the information-processing capacity of the brain. Astrocytes help in the pruning of these excesses of synapses. [65] Astrocytes can also detect and eliminate dysfunctional synapses for improved information processing.

To do so, astrocytes can release factors that promote the engulfment and removal of synapses, leading to a refinement of neural circuits and the optimization of synaptic function. The steps in the mechanism of synaptic pruning can be encapsulated in the following steps—eurological disorders such as autism spectrum disorders and schizophrenia.

1. Recognition of synapses that has to be pruned: Astrocytes are signalled via ATP and platelets-derived growth facts by pericytes that surround blood vessels, oligodendrocytes and neurons. Astrocytes are able to recognize synapses that are essential to be pruned by catching specific signals, such as the complement protein C1q, that are attached to synapses in complement-initiated synaptic pruning which is of apoptotic-like in nature. C1q-tagging of synapses for pruning is confirmed experimentally with apoptotic markers. [66]
2. Release of ATP: The ATP are discharged by astrocytes in response to neuronal activity. Released ATP binds to purinergic receptors on microglia and induces them to release complement proteins.
3. Activation of complement cascade: The complement proteins activate the complement cascade, leading to the formation of the membrane attack complex (MAC). These complementary proteins are released by hepatocytes, neutrophils, macrophages, and other immune cells.
4. Formation of MAC: The formation of MAC involves a series of steps. The C5 convertase cleaves the C5 protein into C5a and C5b after complementary proteins are bound to the synapse. Neely formed C5b induces C6, C7, and C8 to form a complex on the synapse. Among these, C5b and C6 bind to the target membrane, followed by C7

which acts as a linker between C5b-C6 and C8. The complex of C5b-C6-C7- C8 recruits multiple copies of C9 and undergoes conformational changes to form MAC. The MAC punctures the postsynaptic membrane through pore formation. [67]

5. Role of astrocytes: Complement proteins such as C3a and C5a can act as anaphylatoxins, which attach to their respective receptors on the periphery of cells such as astrocytes, and activate downstream signaling pathways leading to the release of cytokines, chemokines, and other inflammatory mediators. [68] In addition, astrocytes can direct complement regulatory proteins that help to avert excessive complement activation and limit damage to surrounding tissues. One example is CD59, which inhibits the formation of MAC by preventing the assembly of C9 molecules into the complex.[69]
6. Engulfment of synapses by astrocytes: Once the astrocytes recognize the synapses to be pruned, they extend their processes to engulf and isolate the synapses from the rest of the neuronal network. Although engulfing synapses was primarily associated with microglia, astrocytes have also been found to actively do so. The phagocytotic ability of astrocytes has been already studied in vitro [70, 71] and in vivo models of injury. [72] During phagocytosis, astrocytes extend their processes and form membrane extensions called phagocytic cups, which surround and engulf the pruned synapses. [73] The phagocytic cups are formed by the reorganization of cytoskeletal proteins like actin and myosin, and the recruitment of membrane-associated proteins like integrins and tetraspanins. Astrocytic extensions cause the internalization of the synapse and further, its systematic degradation. This astrocytic engulfment protects other neurons from contact-induced apoptosis. [74]
7. Recycling of cellular components: The cellular components from the pruned synapses are then degraded using enzymes like proteases, lipases, and nucleases and recycled into new biomolecules by the astrocytes and used for the maintenance and repair of other neuronal structures.

Recent studies have shown that astrocytes are involved in the elimination of synapses by signalling complement C1q expression as described above via transforming growth factor beta (TGF-β) signalling in retinal ganglion cells (RGCs). This mechanism involves both direct and indirect mechanisms. C1q is coded by the C1qa gene in astrocytes and secreted by astrocyte channels in response to signals from injured or stressed neurons. The exact identification of these channels is not clear but they may be calcium-permeable channels that are activated by various

signaling pathways in astrocytes. C1q primarily binds on the surface of postsynaptic membranes to mark them for further elimination. TGF-β is produced and secreted by microglia and other immune cells in response to C1q binding. TGF-β signals to nearby astrocytes to upregulate the expression of phagocytic receptors, such as MEGF10 and MERTK. The increased expression of phagocytic receptors allows astrocytes to engulf and remove the tagged synapses more efficiently. [75]

As it has already been stated previously, in recent years, research has highlighted the crucial role of astrocytes in synaptic pruning. Dysregulation of synaptic pruning by astrocytes has been implicated in various neurological disorders such as autism spectrum disorders and schizophrenia.

Table 2: Inferences on Synaptic Pruning Based on Astrocyte Research:

Research	Results	Inference
Chung et al. (2013) [76]	The study concluded that astrocytes actively partake in synaptic pruning in the developing brain by releasing the protein thrombospondin-1 (TSP-1), which binds to the neuronal surface protein, α2δ-1, and leads to the internalization of AMPA receptors, resulting in the elimination of synapses.	Astrocytes play a critical role in synaptic pruning during brain development through the secretion of TSP-1.
Koeppen et al (2018) [77]	The study found that astrocytes regulate synaptic pruning with the release of ephrin-B1 that interacts with the EphB2 receptor on dendritic spines to induce spine retraction and synaptic elimination.	Astrocytes play a significant role in synaptic pruning through the release of ephrin-B1.
S Koizumi et al (2018) [78]	The study found that astrocytes regulate synaptic pruning through their involvement in the tripartite synapse, which is the interaction between astrocytes, neurons, and synapses. In neurodegenerative diseases, the function of	Astrocyte dysfunction in the tripartite synapse can lead to synaptic pruning and cognitive decline in neurodegenerative diseases.

	astrocytes in synaptic pruning is disrupted, leading to synapse loss and cognitive decline.	
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VIII. ASTROCYTES AS A LOGICAL SWITCH

A logical switch is a mechanical understanding of information processing by neurons by which several inputs are integrated to generate an output based on predetermined rules. Various studies centred around astrocyte functioning have inferred astrocytes to play a significant role in neural transduction. This has led to their inclusion as an integral part of neural circuits that can either amplify or suppress neural activity.

The implications of these findings are significant, as they challenge the traditional view of neurons as the sole mediators of neural function. The involvement of astrocytes in neural circuitry suggests that they may be an important target for therapeutic interventions in neurological disorders, such as epilepsy, Alzheimer's disease, and Parkinson's disease.

Fig. 4. Astrocyte-associated synaptic pruning. (a) ATP released by neurons, oligodendrocytes, microglia and platelet-derived growth factor (PDGF) by pericytes signal astrocytes to participate in synaptic pruning. (b) Astrocytes associate in secreting complementary proteins and undergo a series of responses that include activation of successive proteins shown in a green dot in the figure and cleavage of successive proteins shown in red. (c) C5b, C6, C7, C8, and C9s are complement proteins responsible in the formation of the membrane attack complex (MAC). (d) MAC forms a pore on its target cell that

leads to an influx of water and ions, ultimately causing its destruction

Astrocytes have been found to participate in brain state [79] and neuromodulation [80, 81, 82], and play a crucial role in a variety of naturally occurring recurrent circuits, where they are proposed to carry out spatiotemporal integration of multicellular inputs [83]. Studies have shown that astrocytes are capable of discrimination and integration of synaptic information [84].

There have also been a limited number of studies that have investigated the use of astrocyte-based computations in the context of artificial intelligence. [85, 86]

In conclusion, the role of astrocytes as a logical switch in neural circuitry is an exciting and rapidly evolving field of research. Understanding the mechanisms underlying astrocyte-neuron communication and their implications for brain function and disease has the potential to transform our understanding of the brain and improve treatments for neurological disorders.

IX. FUTURE PROSPECTS IN ASTROGLIAL RESEARCH

Research in astrocytes surely is promising at delivering results that could help humanity through better treatment of neurological disorders and providing an improved understanding of the human brain. As we master CRISPR/Cas9 technology for precise editing of genes, it could be a crucial tool to explain the functions of specific genes in astrocytes and potentially correct genetic defects that cause neurological disorders. As astrocytes show exceptional significance in preserving a healthy network of neuronal systems, if damaged, stem cell therapy could be used to generate astrocytes in vitro and transplant them into the brain to replace damaged or diseased astrocytes and also to promote neural repair. Future research could investigate the potential of modulating astrocyte-mediated immune responses to treat autoimmune and inflammatory neurological disorders. Research of a similar kind could also explore the role of astrocyte networks in brain function and dysfunction, which could lead to new insights into neurological disorders.

The exact purpose of many biomolecules including a significant class of neurotransmitters called gliotransmitters is still an active area of research and remains somewhat controversial. Also various other biomolecules like Integrin $\alpha 6 \beta 1$, a surface protein and Erythropoietin (EPO), a hormone-like protein somewhat remain in the dark when comes to their contribution to astrocyte development and neuroprotection. The same goes for other biomolecules such as Chitinase-3-like

protein 1, Sulfatide, Thrombospondin-1, Neuroligin-2, and Annexin A7.

Astrocyte research could help in the treatment of a large spectrum of diseases like neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's, traumatic brain injuries, schizophrenia, multiple sclerosis, autism spectrum disorders, brain tumours, depression and drug addiction. Further research on the role of astrocytes in influencing circadian rhythm may also lead to new therapeutic approaches for treating sleep disorders. Understanding the functions and mechanisms of astrocytes in developmental biology can also provide insights into potential therapeutic targets for neurodevelopmental disorders.

Additionally, as astrocytes are involved in regulating brain development, understanding their role could lead to new insights into how the overall brain works and how it responds to different stimuli. This could have implications for a wide range of fields, from cognitive neuroscience to artificial intelligence. All in all, astrocyte research could open a variety of possibilities that could equip humanity with better neural health and a wide range of novel discoveries that could contribute to a plethora of biological and technological domains.

X. CONCLUSION

In light of the multifaceted role that astrocytes play in the brain, it is clear that further research in this field is essential. Future investigations could focus on identifying additional molecular mechanisms underlying astrocyte functions, such as their involvement in the modulation of synaptic plasticity and their contribution to neurovascular coupling. Additionally, examining the heterogeneity of astrocytes and their potential for region-specific functions may reveal previously unknown aspects of their contribution to brain physiology and pathology. Such research could provide insights into the fundamental workings of the brain and new targets for therapeutic intervention in neurological disorders.

In conclusion, the study of astrocytes has provided a fascinating perspective on the intricate nature of brain function. From the passive glial cells initially described by Ramón y Cajal to the dynamic and multifaceted cells of today, astrocytes have emerged as key players in the regulation of neural activity and neuroinflammation. The current review has offered a comprehensive overview of historical and recent developments in astrocyte research, highlighting their potential in modulating complex physiological and pathological processes. As we continue to explore the complex biology of astrocytes, we can expect further revelations that will advance our understanding of the brain and contribute to

the development of innovative treatments for neurological disorders.

REFERENCES

- [1] Sofroniew, Michael V., and Harry V. Vinters. "Astrocytes: biology and pathology." *Acta neuropathologica* 119 (2010): 7-35.
- [2] Dong, Yuanshu, and ETTY N. Benveniste. "Immune function of astrocytes." *Glia* 36.2 (2001): 180-190.
- [3] Agulhon, Cendra, et al. "What is the role of astrocyte calcium in neurophysiology?." *Neuron* 59.6 (2008): 932-946.
- [4] Kimelberg, Harold K. "The problem of astrocyte identity." *Neurochemistry international* 45.2-3 (2004): 191-202 p 191.
- [5] DeFelipe, Javier, and Edward G. Jones. "Santiago Ramón y Cajal and methods in neurohistology." *Trends in neurosciences* 15.7 (1992): 237-246.
- [6] Pannese, Ennio. "The Golgi stain: invention, diffusion and impact on neurosciences." *Journal of the History of the Neurosciences* 8.2 (1999): 132-140.
- [7] y Cajal, Santiago Ramón. Algo sobre la significación fisiológica de la neuroglia. *Revist Trimestral Micrografía* (1897): 1, 3–47.
- [8] y Cajal, Ramón. "Contribución al conocimiento de la neuroglia del cerebro humano." *Trab. Lab. Invest. Biol.* 11 (1913): 255.
- [9] Larriva-Sahd, Jorge A. "Some predictions of Rafael Lorente de Nó 80 years later." *Frontiers in Neuroanatomy* 8 (2014): 147.
- [10] Juaristi, Inés, et al. "Extracellular ATP and glutamate drive pyruvate production and energy demand to regulate mitochondrial respiration in astrocytes." *Glia* 67.4 (2019): 759-774.
- [11] Nagy, James I., and John E. Rash. "Connexins and gap junctions of astrocytes and oligodendrocytes in the CNS." *Brain Research Reviews* 32.1 (2000): 29-44.
- [12] Kuffler, Stephen W., and John G. Nicholls. *From neuron to brain*. Sinauer Associates, 1976.
- [13] Theis, Martin, et al. "Emerging complexities in identity and function of glial connexins." *Trends in neurosciences* 28.4 (2005): 188-195.
- [14] Dermietzel, R., et al. "Differential expression of three gap junction proteins in developing and mature brain tissues." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 86.24 (1989): 10148-10152. (The first investigation on the distribution of three connexins in diverse cell populations of the rodent brain involving immunological and developmental analysis.)
- [15] Condorelli, Daniele F., et al. "Cellular expression of connexins in the rat brain: neuronal localization, effects of kainate-induced seizures and expression in apoptotic neuronal cells." *European Journal of Neuroscience* 18.7 (2003): 1807-1827.
- [16] Hofer, A. & Dermietzel, R. Visualization and functional blocking of gap junction hemichannels (connexons) with antibodies against external loop domains in astrocytes. *Glia* 24, 141–154 (1998).

- [17] Contreras, J. E. et al. Metabolic inhibition induces opening of unapposed connexin 43 gap junction hemichannels and reduces gap junctional communication in cortical astrocytes in culture. *Proc. Natl Acad. Sci. USA* 99, 495–500 (2002).
- [18] Laird, Dale W., Christian C. Naus, and Paul D. Lampe. "SnapShot: connexins and disease." *Cell* 170.6 (2017): 1260-1260.
- [19] Scemes, E. Modulation of astrocyte P2Y1 receptors by the carboxyl terminal domain of the gap junction protein Cx43. *Glia* 56, 145–53 (2008).
- [20] Srinivas, Miduturu, Vytas K. Verselis, and Thomas W. White. "Human diseases associated with connexin mutations." *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA)-Biomembranes* 1860.1 (2018): 192-201.
- [21] Zhang, Ye, and Ben A. Barres. "Astrocyte heterogeneity: an underappreciated topic in neurobiology." *Current opinion in neurobiology* 20.5 (2010): 588-594.
- [22] Liddelow, Shane A., and Ben A. Barres. "Reactive astrocytes: production, function, and therapeutic potential." *Immunity* 46.6 (2017): 957-967.
- [23] Weigel, Maya, Lin Wang, and Meng-meng Fu. "Microtubule organization and dynamics in oligodendrocytes, astrocytes, and microglia." *Developmental Neurobiology* 81.3 (2021): 310-320.
- [24] Mazumder, Arpan G., et al. "Astrocyte heterogeneity within white matter tracts and a unique subpopulation of optic nerve head astrocytes." *Iscience* 25.12 (2022): 105568.
- Mi, Huaiyu, Henry Haerberle, and Ben A. Barres. "Induction of astrocyte differentiation by endothelial cells." *Journal of Neuroscience* 21.5 (2001): 1538-1547.
- [25] Oberheim, Nancy Ann, et al. "Uniquely hominid features of adult human astrocytes." *Journal of Neuroscience* 29.10 (2009): 3276-3287.
- [26] Anderson, Mark A., Yan Ao, and Michael V. Sofroniew. "Heterogeneity of reactive astrocytes." *Neuroscience letters* 565 (2014): 23-29.
- [27] Zeisel, Amit, et al. "Cell types in the mouse cortex and hippocampus revealed by single-cell RNA-seq." *Science* 347.6226 (2015): 1138-1142.
- [28] Morel, Lydie, et al. "Molecular and functional properties of regional astrocytes in the adult brain." *Journal of Neuroscience* 37.36 (2017): 8706-8717.
- [29] Chung, Won-Suk, Nicola J. Allen, and Cagla Eroglu. "Astrocytes control synapse formation, function, and elimination." *Cold Spring Harbor perspectives in biology* 7.9 (2015): a020370.
- [30] Cao, Junyue, et al. "Comprehensive single-cell transcriptional profiling of a multicellular organism." *Science* 357.6352 (2017): 661-667.
- [31] Bekar, Lane K., Wei He, and Maiken Nedergaard. "Locus coeruleus α -adrenergic-mediated activation of cortical astrocytes in vivo." *Cerebral cortex* 18.12 (2008): 2789-2795.
- [32] Nimmerjahn, Axel. "Astrocytes going live: advances and challenges." *The Journal of physiology* 587.8 (2009): 1639-1647.
- [33] Perea, Gertrudis, Marta Navarrete, and Alfonso Araque. "Tripartite synapses: astrocytes process and control synaptic information." *Trends in neurosciences* 32.8 (2009): 421-431.
- [34] Schummers, James, Hongbo Yu, and Mriganka Sur. "Tuned responses of astrocytes and their influence on hemodynamic signals in the visual cortex." *Science* 320.5883 (2008): 1638-1643.
- [35] Semyanov, Alexey. "Spatiotemporal pattern of calcium activity in astrocytic network." *Cell calcium* 78 (2019): 15-25.
- [36] Hassinger, T. D., et al. "An extracellular signaling component in propagation of astrocytic calcium waves." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 93.23 (1996): 13268-13273.
- [37] Tzagareli, Merab G., and Ivliane Nozadze. "An overview on transient receptor potential channels superfamily." *Behavioural Pharmacology* 31.5 (2019): 413-434.
- [38] Grimm, Christian, et al. "Two-pore channels: catalyzers of endolysosomal transport and function." *Frontiers in pharmacology* 8 (2017): 45.
- [39] Kim, Warren T., Marika G. Rioult, and Ann H. Cornell-Bell. "Glutamate-induced calcium signaling in astrocytes." *Glia* 11.2 (1994): 173-184.
- [40] Scemes, Eliana, and Christian Giaume. "Astrocyte calcium waves: what they are and what they do." *Glia* 54.7 (2006): 716-725.
- [41] Hamilton, Nicola B., and David Attwell. "Do astrocytes really exocytose neurotransmitters?." *Nature Reviews Neuroscience* 11.4 (2010): 227-238.
- [42] Perea, Gertrudis, and Alfonso Araque. "GLIA modulates synaptic transmission." *Brain research reviews* 63.1-2 (2010): 93-102.
- [43] Goldman, W. F., et al. "Sodium/calcium exchange in rat cortical astrocytes." *Journal of Neuroscience* 14.10 (1994): 5834-5843.
- [44] Skowrońska, Katarzyna, Hanna Kozłowska, and Jan Albrecht. "Neuron-derived factors negatively modulate ryanodine receptor-mediated calcium release in cultured mouse astrocytes." *Cell Calcium* 92 (2020): 102304.
- [45] Dringen, Ralf, Rolf Gebhardt, and Bernd Hamprecht. "Glycogen in astrocytes: possible function as lactate supply for neighboring cells." *Brain research* 623.2 (1993): 208-214.
- [46] Mizuta, Ikuko, et al. "Riluzole stimulates nerve growth factor, brain-derived neurotrophic factor and glial cell line-derived neurotrophic factor synthesis in cultured mouse astrocytes." *Neuroscience letters* 310.2-3 (2001): 117-120.
- [47] Walz, Wolfgang. "Role of astrocytes in the clearance of excess extracellular potassium." *Neurochemistry international* 36.4-5 (2000): 291-300.
- [48] Beckner, Marie E. "A roadmap for potassium buffering/dispersion via the glial network of the CNS." *Neurochemistry international* 136 (2020): 104727.
- [49] Gabriel, Siegrun, et al. "Stimulus and potassium-induced epileptiform activity in the human dentate gyrus from patients with and without hippocampal sclerosis." *Journal of Neuroscience* 24.46 (2004): 10416-10430.
- [50] Olsen, Michelle L., and Harald Sontheimer. "Functional implications for Kir4. 1 channels in glial biology: from

- K⁺ buffering to cell differentiation." *Journal of neurochemistry* 107.3 (2008): 589-601.
- [51] Østby, Ivar, et al. "Astrocytic mechanisms explaining neural-activity-induced shrinkage of extraneuronal space." *PLoS computational biology* 5.1 (2009): e1000272.
- [52] Mongin, Alexander A. "Volume-regulated anion channel—a frenemy within the brain." *Pflügers Archiv-European Journal of Physiology* 468 (2016): 421-441.
- [53] Machado, V., Pinto, M. J., Nogueira, T., Madeira, M. D., Silva, H. B., Silva, A. P., & Marques, J. M. ". Age-related changes in hippocampal astrocytes and their relationship to Alzheimer's disease pathology." *Journal of Neurophysiology* (2019): 130
- [54] Simpson, J. E., et al. "Microglial activation in white matter lesions and nonlesional white matter of ageing brains." *Neuropathology and applied neurobiology* 33.6 (2007): 670-683.
- [55] Rose, Christine R., et al. "Astroglial glutamate signaling and uptake in the hippocampus." *Frontiers in Molecular Neuroscience* 10 (2018): 451.
- [56] Butt, Arthur M. "ATP: a ubiquitous gliotransmitter integrating neuron–glial networks." *Seminars in cell & developmental biology*. Vol. 22. No. 2. Academic Press (2011).
- [57] Hertz, Leif, P. H. Wu, and Arne Schousboe. "Evidence for net uptake of GABA into mouse astrocytes in primary cultures—its sodium dependence and potassium independence." *Neurochemical research* 3 (1978): 313-323.
- [58] Sofroniew, Michael V. "Multiple roles for astrocytes as effectors of cytokines and inflammatory mediators." *The Neuroscientist* 20.2 (2014): 160-172.
- [59] Hertz, Leif, and William E. Code. "Calcium channel signaling in astrocytes." *Calcium antagonists: pharmacology and clinical research* (1993): 205-213.
- [60] Macnab, Madison. *Purinergic Signalling and Potassium Homeostasis Regulate Somatosensory Adaptation*. Diss. University of Saskatchewan (2022).
- [61] Straub, Stephen V., and Mark T. Nelson. "Astrocytic calcium signaling: the information currency coupling neuronal activity to the cerebral microcirculation." *Trends in cardiovascular medicine* 17.6 (2007): 183-190.
- [62] Duffy, S., and B. A. MacVicar. "Potassium-dependent calcium influx in acutely isolated hippocampal astrocytes." *Neuroscience* 61.1 (1994): 51-61.
- [63] Dehnes, Yvette, et al. "The glutamate transporter EAAT4 in rat cerebellar Purkinje cells: a glutamate-gated chloride channel concentrated near the synapse in parts of the dendritic membrane facing astroglia." *Journal of Neuroscience* 18.10 (1998): 3606-3619.
- [64] Bosworth, Alexandra P., and Nicola J. Allen. "The diverse actions of astrocytes during synaptic development." *Current Opinion in Neurobiology* 47 (2017): 38-43.
- [65] Kovács, Réka Á., et al. "Identification of neuronal pentraxins as synaptic binding partners of C1q and the involvement of NP1 in synaptic pruning in adult mice." *Frontiers in immunology* 11 (2021): 599771.
- [66] Barnum, Scott R., Doryen Bubeck, and Theresa N. Schein. "Soluble membrane attack complex: Biochemistry and immunobiology." *Frontiers in Immunology* (2020): 2891.
- [67] Sayah, S., et al. "Two different transduction pathways are activated by C3a and C5a anaphylatoxins on astrocytes." *Molecular brain research* 112.1-2 (2003): 53-60.
- [68] Sugita, Yuji, and Yasuhiko Masuho. "CD59: its role in complement regulation and potential for therapeutic use." *Immunotechnology* 1.3-4 (1995): 157-168.
- [69] Park, J., Wetzel, I., Marriott, I. et al. A 3D human triculture system modeling neurodegeneration and neuroinflammation in Alzheimer's disease. *Nat Neurosci* 21 (2018): 941–951.
- [70] Lee, Se Young, and Won-Suk Chung. "The roles of astrocytic phagocytosis in maintaining homeostasis of brains." *Journal of Pharmacological Sciences* 145.3 (2021): 223-227.
- [71] Al-Ali, S. Y., and S. M. Al-Hussain. "An ultrastructural study of the phagocytic activity of astrocytes in adult rat brain." *Journal of anatomy* 188.Pt 2 (1996): 257.
- [72] Geloso, Maria Concetta, and Nadia D'Ambrosi. "Microglial pruning: relevance for synaptic dysfunction in multiple sclerosis and related experimental models." *Cells* 10.3 (2021): 686.
- [73] Lööv, Camilla, et al. "Engulfing astrocytes protect neurons from contact-induced apoptosis following injury." *PloS one* 7.3 (2012): e33090.
- [74] Bialas, Allison R., and Beth Stevens. "Retracted article: TGF- β signaling regulates neuronal C1q expression and developmental synaptic refinement." *Nature neuroscience* 16.12 (2013): 1773-1782.
- [75] Chung, W. S., Allen, N. J., Eroglu, C., & Barres, B. A. "Thrombospondin-1 modulates synaptic plasticity by regulating AMPA receptor trafficking." *Neuron*, 79(3) (2013): 645-662.
- [76] Koeppen, Jordan, et al. "Functional consequences of synapse remodeling following astrocyte-specific regulation of Ephrin-B1 in the adult hippocampus." *Journal of Neuroscience* 38.25 (2018): 5710-5726.
- [77] Koizumi, Schuichi. "Astrocyte-synapse interaction in health and diseases." *Proceedings for Annual Meeting of The Japanese Pharmacological Society WCP2018 (The 18th World Congress of Basic and Clinical Pharmacology)*. Japanese Pharmacological Society, 2018.
- [78] Poskanzer, K. E., & Yuste, R. "Astrocytes regulate cortical state switching in vivo." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*. (2016): 113(19)
- [79] Magistretti, P. J., & Morrison, J. H. "Noradrenaline- and vasoactive intestinal peptide-containing neuronal systems in neocortex: Functional convergence with contrasting morphology." *Neuroscience*, 24(2) (1998): 367–37
- [80] Paukert, M., Agarwal, A., Cha, J., Doze, V. A., Kang, J. U., & Bergles, D. E. "Norepinephrine controls astroglial responsiveness to local circuit activity." *Neuron*, 82(6) (2014):1263–1270.
- [81] Srinivasan, R., Huang, B. S., Venugopal, S., Johnston, A. D., Chai, H., Zeng, H., ... Khakh, B. S. "Ca(2+) signaling in astrocytes from *Ip3r2(-/-)* mice in brain slices and

- during startle responses in vivo." *Nature Neuroscience*, 18(5) (2015): 708–717.
- [82] Araque, A., Carmignoto, G., Haydon, P. G., Oliet, S. H., Robitaille, R., & Volterra, A. Gliotransmitters travel in time and space. *Neuron*, 81(4), (2014): 728–739.
- [83] Perea, G., & Araque. "Properties of synaptically evoked astrocyte calcium signal reveal synaptic information processing by astrocytes." *The Journal of Neuroscience*, 25(9) (2015): 2192–2203.
- [84] Alvarellos-Gonzalez, A., Pazos, A., & Porto-Pazos. "Computational models of neuron-astrocyte interactions Lead to improved efficiency in the performance of neural networks." *Computational and Mathematical Methods in Medicine*, 2012 (2015): 1–10.
- [85] Porto-Pazos, A. B., Veigueta, N., Mesejo, P., Navarrete, M., Alvarellos, A., Ibanez, O., ... Araque, A. "Artificial astrocytes improve neural network performance." *PLoS One*, 6(4) (2011): e19109.